

PHOTOCHEMICAL REACTIONS WITH SOME INORGANIC COLLOIDS AS ACTIVE AGENTS UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF LIGHT IN VARIOUS STATES OF POLARISATION. PART II. PHOTOCHEMICAL REDUCTION OF TUNGSTIC ACID SOL BY GLUCOSE, LAEVULOSE, FORMALDEHYDE, LACTIC ACID, SODIUM HYPOPHOSPHITE, LEUCINE, AND GLUTAMIC ACID.

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The experimental arrangement and a portion of the experimental procedure have been described in Part I of this series. Special precautions were taken so that during the process of photoreduction, the reacting system did not come in contact with oxygen.

The sol was prepared from sodium tungstate and hydrochloric acid (Merck's reagent). In each case the amount of acid was sufficient to bring the p_H of the prepared sol to about 1.5. In case of amino-acids the reductant was dissolved in the minimum amount of hydrochloric acid (in a known volume) and the two solutions were mixed together. The sol prepared in this way showed no visible turbidity due to coagulation during the period of investigation. It is of particular importance to note that in all our experiments, the concentration of sol has been expressed in terms of the concentration of the tungstate used for the preparation of sol.

Determination of the Velocity of Reaction.

Spectrophotometric method was applied for the estimation of the reduced tungstic acid sol. For this purpose a König-Martens spectrophotometer was first calibrated in the following way:—

The cell was filled with the reaction mixture containing the reductant in excess and tungstic acid sol of known concentration and the absorption of the reaction mixture was taken in the green ($525 \mu\mu$). The corresponding reading θ_1 , on the circular scale of the spectrophotometer was recorded which was evidently the zero-reading. The cell with the reaction mixture was then exposed to sunlight. After each half an hour, the absorption of the reduced tungstic acid sol was read by the spectrophotometer, the wave-length setting always remaining the same. The process was repeated until the spectrophotometer gave constant reading θ_2 , which was evidently the final reading corresponding to the complete reduction of the tungstic

acid sol. In this way, a set of readings θ_2 was obtained with different concentration of tungstic acid sol. The final value of θ_2 was found to be independent of p_H within the range 1.0–5.0.

Different concentrations of the tungstic acid sol and corresponding spectrophotometer readings θ_2 , after complete reduction of the sol, are tabulated in Table I.

TABLE I.

Zero reading (θ_1) = 45°.

Conc. of sol(N)	...	0.007	0.006	0.005	0.004	0.003	0.002	0.001
Final reading θ_2	...	71°.5	69°.0	65°.8	61°.5	58°.0	53°.3	48°.8
$\log \tan \theta_2 - \log \tan \theta_1$	...	0.4755	0.4158	0.3450	0.2652	0.2042	0.1276	0.0578

$\log \tan \theta_2 - \log \tan \theta_1$ was plotted against the corresponding concentration of tungstic acid sol. A straight line was obtained (Fig. 1) as was to be expected. From this standard curve, the concentration of the reduced tungstic acid sol at any time during the course of our experiment was determined by taking the spectrophotometer reading at 525 $\mu\mu$.

FIG. 1.

Determination of p_H .—The p_H of the reaction mixture was determined potentiometrically by using quinhydrone electrode. In cases, where concentrations of sol and reductants were varied at the same p_H , the p_H of each

set of experiments was brought to the same value within ± 0.01 by trial by addition of required quantities of hydrochloric acid.

Study of the Light Reaction.—Tungstic acid sol is not reduced by any of the above mentioned reductants in the dark.

Determination of the Order of Reaction.

TABLE II.

Tungstate = $0.05M$. Leucine = 1%. Temp. = $29^{\circ}5$. $p_H = 1.67$. $I_{abs.}$ = Intensity of radiation ($366\mu\mu$) absorbed in ergs per sq. cm. per sec. = 2925. d (thickness of the cell) = 0.5 cm.

Time.	Spectrophotometric reading.	Conc. of reduced sol $\times 10^3$.	$K_{zero-mol.} \times 10^4$.
(a) 0 min.	$45^{\circ}0$	0	
(b) 27	$48^{\circ}2$	0.70	0.430 (from a and b)
(c) 54	$51^{\circ}7$	1.5	0.493 (from b and c)
(d) 80	$54^{\circ}7$	2.22	0.478 (from b and d)
(e) 106	$58^{\circ}0$	3.05	0.495 (from b and e)

From the above table it is evident that the velocity constant of the photochemical reduction is zero-molecular with respect to sol. Other photo-reductions also obey the zero-molecular law. The zero-molecular velocity constants have been expressed in terms of number of g. mols transformed in 1 sec. in a unit cell (1 cm. $\times$ 1 cm. $\times$ 1 cm.).

Induction Period.—In the case of leucine and sodium hypophosphite the induction period is small but in all other cases it is rather high. Passing nitrogen gas through the reaction mixture to expel dissolved oxygen has been found to diminish the induction period effectively and this has been generally done. In some cases, e.g., glutamic acid where the induction period is very large (several hours) it was overcome by a preliminary exposure of the reaction mixture to total radiation of mercury lamp. The value of velocity constant noted in the following tables are those observed after the induction period is over.

Pure nitrogen was prepared by heating ammonium chloride and sodium nitrite and by passing the gas through caustic soda solution, alkaline pyrogallol acid and water.

Effect of Varying the Concentration of the Reductant.

TABLE III.

 $d=0.5$ cm. γ =Quantum efficiency. I_{abs} = Intensity of the absorbed radiation in ergs per sq. cm. per sec.(a) Temp. = 29.5°. $I_{abs} = 1166$.
Tungstate = 0.05M. $p_H = 1.24$ (b) Temp. = 29.5°. $I_{abs} = 1432$.
Tungstate = 0.05M. $p_H = 1.24$ Conc. of
reductant. $K \times 10^3$. γ .Conc. of
reductant. $K \times 10^3$. γ .

Formaldehyde.

Glucose.

0.8425M	1.107	1.55
0.4213	0.827	1.16
0.2106	0.552	0.78
0.1053	0.332	0.45

10%	1.007	1.15
5	0.743	0.85
2.5	0.467	0.53

(c) Temp. = 30°. $I_{abs} = 1330$.
Tungstate = 0.025M. $p_H = 1.48$ (d) Temp. = 30°. $I_{abs} = 1330$.
Tungstate = 0.025M. $p_H = 1.18$

Laevulose.

Lactic acid.

10 %	0.898	1.21
5	0.630	0.78
2.5	0.370	0.46

1.01M	1.277	1.57
0.606	0.933	1.15
0.253	0.535	0.66

(e) Temp. = 29.5°. $I_{abs} = 1330$.
Tungstate = 0.025M. $p_H = 1.29$.(f) Temp. = 31°. $I_{abs} = 1938$.
Tungstate = 0.05M. $p_H = 1.72$

Mandelic acid.

Sodium hypophosphite.

M/2	0.505	0.62
M/4	0.483	0.60
M/8	0.450	0.55

0.0830M	1.437	1.18
0.0415	1.117	0.92
0.0207	0.772	0.64
0.0103	0.477	0.39
0.00824	0.388	0.32

(g) Temp. = 29.5°. $I_{abs} = 2722$.
Tungstate = 0.05M. $p_H = 1.69$ (h) Temp. = 29.5°. $I_{abs} = 2632$.
Tungstate = 0.05M. $p_H = 1.33$

Leucine.

Glutamic acid.

1.998 %	0.472	0.28
1.333	0.455	0.27
0.666	0.460	0.27
0.45	0.465	0.27

2 %	0.260	0.16
1.5	0.227	0.14
1	0.192	0.12
0.5	0.113	0.07

In the case of leucine, the variation of concentration has got practically no effect on the reaction velocity. In all other cases, when $1/K$ is plotted against $1/C_{\text{reductant}}$, a straight line is obtained. It is to be noted however that in this case the velocity constant with only 0.4% leucine is much larger than that obtained with 2% glutamic acid (Fig. 2).

FIG. 2.

Effect of Varying the Concentration of Sol.

TABLE IV.

 $d = 0.5 \text{ cm.}$

Temp.	$I_{\text{abs.}}$	Tungstate.	p_{H}	Reductant used.	$K_1 \times 10^3$.	γ .
(a)				Formaldehyde.		
29.5°	1166	0.050M	1.24	0.8425 M	1.108	1.25
"	"	0.0375	"	"	1.113	1.56
"	"	0.025	"	"	1.083	1.31
(b)				Glucose.		
29.5°	1432	0.05	1.24	10 %	1.007	1.15
"	"	0.0375	"	"	1.022	1.17
"	"	0.025	"	"	1.000	1.14
(c)				Lævulose.		
30°	1330	0.025	1.48	5 %	0.630	0.78
"	"	0.0125	1.47	"	0.605	0.75
(d)				Lactic acid.		
30°	1330	0.025	1.18	1.01 M	1.277	1.57
"	"	0.0125	"	"	1.278	1.57
(e)				Mandelic acid.		
29.5°	1331	0.025	1.43	M/4	0.497	0.61
"	"	0.0125	"	M/4	0.492	0.60

TABLE IV (contd.).

 $d = 0.5$ cm.

Temp.	$I_{abs.}$	Tungstate.	p_H .	Reductant used.	$K_0 \times 10^3$.	γ .
(f)				Sodium hypophosphite.		
31°	1904	0.075 M	1.73	0.1245 M	1.675	1.38
"	1890	0.05	"	"	1.608	1.36
"	1873	0.025	"	"	1.525	1.31
(g)				Lencine.		
29.5°	2743	0.075	1.55	0.66 %	0.533	0.32
"	2722	0.05	"	"	0.500	0.30
"	2698	0.025	"	"	0.485	0.29
"	2641	0.0125	"	"	0.467	0.28
(h)				Glutamic acid.		
29.5°	2677	0.075	1.33	2 %	0.272	0.16
"	2632	0.05	"	"	0.260	0.16
"	2610	0.025	"	"	0.250	0.15

In all cases the quantum yield of the photoreductions, under otherwise identical conditions, has been found to be practically independent of sol concentration.

Effect of Varying the Temperature.

TABLE V.

With formaldehyde.

Temp.	$I_{abs.}$	Tungstate.	p_H .	Reductant.	$K_0 \times 10^3$.	Temp. coeff. $\frac{K_{T-10}}{K_T}$.
29.5°	1620	0.025M	1.24	0.8425M	1.683	1.14
39.5	"	"	"	"	1.917	

With other reductants also, the temperature coefficient was small being of the order of 1.00-1.15.

Effect of Varying the Intensity of Radiation Absorbed.

TABLE VI.

$d=0.5$ cm.

Temp.	I_{abs}	Tungstate.	Reductant.	μ_r	$K_0 \times 10^3$.
(a)			Formaldehyde.		
29.5°	1166	0.05M	0.8425%	1.24	1.108
"	572	"	"	"	0.553
(b)			Glucose.		
29.5°	1432	0.05	20%	1.24	1.007
"	1028	"	"	"	0.775
(c)			Laevalnose.		
30°	1331	0.025	5%	1.48	0.630
"	918	"	"	"	0.438
(d)			Lactic acid.		
30°	1331	0.025	1.01%	1.18	1.277
"	444	"	"	"	0.420
(e)			Mandelic acid.		
29.5°	1140	0.025	M/4	1.43	0.497
"	502	"	"	"	0.220
(f)			Sodium hypophosphite.		
31°	1748	0.05	0.0415N	1.76	0.975
"	1073	"	"	"	0.580
(g)			Leucine.		
29.5°	2925	0.05	0.666%	1.69	0.500
"	1755	"	"	"	0.285
(h)			Glutamic acid.		
29.5°	2631	0.05	2%	1.33	0.260
"	1305	"	"	"	0.133

The rate of reaction, under otherwise identical conditions, is proportional to the intensity of radiation absorbed.

Quantum Efficiency of the Photoreductions.

A typical example for calculating the quantum efficiency of the process is given below.

In Table II, the intensity of radiation ($366 \mu\mu$) absorbed in ergs per sq. cm. per sec. by a column of solution 0.5 cm thick = 2925 ergs

$$= \frac{2925 \times 366 \times 10^{-7}}{(6.55 \times 10^{-27}) \times (3 \times 10^{10}) \times (6.1 \times 10^{23})} \quad \text{Einsteins.}$$

$$= 8.933 \times 10^{10} \text{ Einsteins.}$$

The zero-molecular velocity constant K (expressed in terms of no. of g. mol. transformed in sec. in a unit cell of 1 cm. $\times$ 1 cm. $\times$ 1 cm.) = 0.488×10^{-9} .

No. of g. mol transformed in 1 sec. in a cell of 1 cm. $\times$ 1 cm. $\times$ 0.5 cm

$$= 0.244 \times 10^{-9}.$$

Quantum efficiency of the process

$$= \frac{0.244 \times 10^{-9}}{8.933 \times 10^{10}}$$

$$= 0.2735.$$

Quantum yield for the other experiments were similarly calculated.

Observations when Reactions were Carried in Polarised Light ($366 \mu\mu$).

In these experiments the reacting system, immediately after mixing the reactants, was exposed to radiation polarised in the way stated, and the velocity of reaction measured after the induction period was over. In the case of exposure to *d*- or *l*-circularly polarised light, the induction period was about 8 hours,

TABLE VII.

$d = 0.5$ cm. γ = quantum efficiency

I_{abs} = Intensity of radiation absorbed per sq. cm. per sec.

(a) Temp. = 30°. Tungstate = 0.025M. Formaldehyde = 0.8425M. $p_H = 1.48$.				(b) Temp. = 29.5°. Glucose = 5%. Tungstate = 0.025 M. $p_H = 1.95$.			
State of polarisation.	I_{abs} .	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$.	γ .	State of polarisation.	I_{abs} .	$K \times 10^{10}$.	γ .
<i>l</i> -Circularly polarised	237	1.39	0.96	Unpolarised	1432	4.10	0.47
<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised	237	0.95	0.66	<i>l</i> -Circularly polarised	237	0.70	0.48
Unpolarised	1170	0.65	0.93	<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised	237	0.40	0.26
(c) Temp. = 30°. Laevulose = 5%. Tungstate = 0.025M. $p_H = 1.94$.				(d) Temp. = 30°. Lactic acid = 1.01M. Tungstate = 0.025M. $p_H = 1.18$.			
Unpolarised	1331	4.51	0.54	Unpolarised	1331	12.77	1.57
<i>l</i> -Circularly polarised	180	0.61	0.55	<i>l</i> -Circularly polarised	195	1.87	1.57
<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised	180	0.44	0.40	<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised	195	1.28	1.08
(e) Temp. = 30°. Mandelic acid = M/4. Tungstate = 0.025M. $p_H = 1.43$.				(f) Temp. = 29.5°. Leucine = 0.666%. Tungstate = 0.05M. $p_H = 1.33$.			
Unpolarised	1331	5.0	0.61	Unpolarised	2081	4.35	0.335
<i>l</i> -Circularly polarised	328	1.22	0.61	<i>l</i> -Circularly polarised	385	0.79	0.329
<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised	328	0.87	0.43	<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised	385	0.67	0.278
(g) Temp. = 31°. Hypophosphite = 0.12M. Tungstate = 0.05M. $p_H = 1.75$.							
Unpolarised					1085	8.60	1.87
<i>l</i> -Circularly polarised					192	1.54	1.28
<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised					192	1.34	1.20

(h) As the induction period with glutamic acid as reductant was very large (several hours), the reaction was not studied in polarised light.

It is evident from the above tables that in all cases

$$V_o = V_L > V_D,$$

where V_o , V_L and V_D stand for velocity of reaction in unpolarised, *l*-circularly polarised and *d*-circularly polarised light respectively.

Observations on the Photoreductions with Pre-activated Tungstic Acid Sol.

Here tungstic acid sol, prepared by the action of hydrochloric acid on sodium tungstate as stated before, was first exposed in an atmosphere of nitrogen to ultraviolet rays for a sufficiently long time (about 3 hours) and mixed immediately with the reductant. The reaction (photoreduction) was then allowed to proceed in the ultraviolet light ($366\mu\mu$) also in an atmosphere of nitrogen.

TABLE VIII.

$d = 0.5$ cm. Tungstate = $0.025M$. Glucose = 10%. $I_{abs} = 585$.
 $p_H = 1.24$. Temp. = 31° .

Time.	Conc. of reduced tungstate $\times 10^3$.	$K_0 \times 10^3$.	γ .
(1) 0 sec.	0		
(2) 32	0.89	0.462 (from 1 & 2)	
(3) 64	1.72	0.447 (from 1 & 3)	
(4) 96	2.55	0.442 (from 1 & 4)	1.25
(5) 122	3.25	0.443 (from 1 & 5)	
		Mean. 0.448	

We have noticed before that when unactivated sol was used, the reaction was zero-molecular and attended with a large initial period of induction even when the reaction proceeded in an atmosphere of nitrogen. On using the pre-activated sol in an atmosphere of nitrogen, the order of reaction remained the same but the induction period was eliminated completely. It must be noted that if the reaction proceeded in presence of air, pre-activation of the sol alone can not totally eliminate the induction period.

Table IX shows that by the process of pre-activation, the quantum efficiency is not modified to an appreciable extent.

TABLE IX.

Temp. = 31°. Tungstate = 0.025M. Glucose = 10%.

Nature of sol used.	I_{abs}	$\dot{p}_n$	$K_1 \times 10^3$	γ
Not preactivated	2440	1.25	1.717	1.23
Pre-activated	585	1.24	0.448	1.25

DISCUSSION.

The reactions have the following characteristics :—

(1) It is zero-molecular with respect to the sol. The concentration of sol within the limit studied in our experiments having practically no influence on the quantum efficiency of the photochemical process and the absorption of radiation $366\mu\mu$ by sol within this limit is practically complete.

(2) Zero-molecular velocity constant is proportional to the light energy absorbed.

(3) Quantum yield of the photochemical process varies practically between 1 and 0.1.

(4) The inverse of the velocity constant plotted against the inverse of the concentration of reductant gives a straight line.

(5) The temperature coefficient of the velocity constant is nearly unity.

(6) *l*-Circularly polarised light gives a higher quantum yield under otherwise identical conditions than the *d*-circularly polarised light.

All these characteristic features can be explained by the assumption that radiations absorbed by tungstic acid particles on the sol surface create active centres for oxidation on that surface. If within the life period of these active centres, a molecule of reductant collides with them it undergoes oxidation.

The rate of reaction is proportional to the number of such active centres created per second and the surface concentration of the reductant.

$$\text{Hence } dx/dt = I/Nh\nu \times C_s^a$$

where C_s^a is the surface concentration of reductants.

But according to Langmuir's hypothesis, surface concentration of the

reductant is

$$\frac{K_1 C_n^n}{K_2 C_n^n + I}$$

where C_n^n is the concentration of the reductants in the solution.

Therefore,
$$dx/dt = \frac{I}{Nh\nu} \times \frac{K_1 C_n^n}{I + K_2 C_n^n}$$

or
$$\frac{I}{dx/dt} = \frac{Nh\nu}{I} \left[\frac{K_2}{K_1} + \frac{I}{K_1 C_n^n} \right] = \left[\frac{I}{K} + \frac{I}{K' C_n^n} \right]$$

for constant value of $\frac{I}{Nh\nu}$

We have already seen that the inverse of the velocity constant plotted against the inverse of the concentration of the reductant is a straight line as is demanded by the above equation.

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